

Skin Temperature Sampling Period for Longitudinal Thermal Comfort Studies

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SUMMARY

There is limited scientific evidence on what is the optimal sampling period to measure skin temperature in longitudinal thermal comfort studies, and how this sampling period selection affects the results. iButtons® are among the most widely used wireless sensors in field and lab studies to measure skin temperature, since they are accurate, reliable, and cause minimal discomfort. However, their use is significantly limited by their memory capacity. We aimed to determine what is the optimal sampling period of skin temperature in studies which use iButtons®. We measured wrist skin temperature of 14 participants at 60 s intervals for a period of 1 month and wrist temperature of 5 participants at 20 s intervals for a week. Results showed that the selection of a 300 s sampling period would provide reasonably accurate results while limiting the number of times data needs to be downloaded.

KEYWORDS

physiological signals, thermophysiology, wireless sensors, non-intrusive measurement, skin temperature

1 INTRODUCTION

The Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and the adaptive thermal comfort models are widely used in thermal comfort research and have been adopted by most of the international standards. However, both models have severe limitations in real world applications and poor prediction accuracy (Cheung et al., 2019). Many building occupants find the indoor environment uncomfortable. A study conducted in the US reported that approximately 43% of 52,980 people surveyed in 351 office buildings were thermally dissatisfied (Karmann et al., 2018). Thermal discomfort due to overcooling or overheating may not only increase the overall energy consumption in buildings, but may also negatively impact occupants' health and productivity (Fisk and Rosenfeld, 1997; Wargocki et al., 2000). To find a solution to this problem, numerous research groups have started investigating a new approach, moving away from aggregate models such as the PMV and focusing on the development of personalized thermal comfort models (Kim et al., 2018a). This approach tries to predict an individual's thermal comfort response, instead of the average response of a large population. It leverages the fact that Internet of Things sensors and wearables are becoming low cost and ubiquitous. It uses machine learning to predict individual's comfort requirements and preferences. Personalized thermal comfort models overcome two other major limitations of existing comfort models have: they are dynamic, hence, can be re-trained as new data is collected, and they do not have a set limit of independent variables. Personalized thermal comfort models may also be aggregated to predict comfort of a population (Kim et al., 2018a, 2018b). Personalized thermal comfort models may use physiological data as input, among which an important one is skin temperature, T_{sk} . T_{sk} in the extremities reflects the vasomotor tone and when vasoconstriction occurs T_{sk} decreases towards air temperature, whereas when vasodilation takes place T_{sk} increases towards the core temperature (Romanovsky, 2018). Vasoconstriction and vasodilation are physiological

mechanisms that the human body uses for thermoregulation. Previous laboratories and field studies have shown that T_{sk} may be used as an independent variable in thermal comfort models to improve their prediction accuracy (Choi et al., 2012; Lan et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019). However, while there is enough evidence supporting the hypothesis that T_{sk} can enhance thermal comfort models prediction accuracy, we found that there is limited scientific evidence on what is the optimal sampling period to measure T_{sk} in longitudinal thermal comfort studies, and how the selected sampling period affects the results. Review of the available thermal comfort literature showed that T_{sk} was sampled over a wide domain of intervals ranging from 1 to 600 s in different studies (Aryal and Becerik-Gerber, 2019; Lan et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019; Rutkove et al., 2007; Sarabia et al., 2008; Schellen et al., 2010; Tsuzuki et al., 2008; van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006; Xiong et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2017). Only few of the authors justified the rationale behind their selection. Arguably, their selection may have been driven by convenience. Researches who used wired sensors connected to a central data logger, generally acquired data at 1 s intervals. This method can be used for laboratories studies, since battery life, memory capacity and intrusiveness are generally not considered to be an issue. In most of the laboratory studies T_{sk} is only monitored for few hours. In field studies, the use of wired sensors it is impractical and it is generally a source of discomfort for participants who need to wear the sensor on a daily-basis. As a result, in longitudinal studies T_{sk} was recorded over a wide range of sampling periods between 1 and 10 minutes. This may have a significant impact on the results since long sampling intervals may cause data loss. Another limitation that we faced at the time when we conducted this study was that there were only few sensors available that could non-intrusively monitor T_{sk} . Wristbands and smartwatches available in the market claimed to accurately measure physiological parameters, however, the great majority of them were not accurate or not designed to measure T_{sk} (Liu et al., 2019). iButtons® were one of the few wireless sensors that had been previously validated and had been proven to accurately measure T_{sk} . iButtons® are wireless data loggers and are a practical alternative to other more bulky and intrusive sensors to obtain accurate measurements of T_{sk} in field and laboratory studies (Hasselberg et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2019; van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006). However, their use in longitudinal studies is limited by their memory capacity and minimum sampling interval. Two main iButtons® version were available in the market that could be used in a longitudinal study to measure T_{sk} . The model DS1925 could store a total of 61K readings taken at minimum sampling period of 300 s and the model DS1922 that was capable of storing 4096 readings at sampling periods of 1 s. The former had enough memory to log data for a period of approximately 211 days while the latter could only log data for less than 3 consecutive days if sampling at 1 minute intervals. We, therefore, aimed to determine how the selection of the sampling period affects the errors in the results in longitudinal thermal comfort field studies that utilize skin temperature wireless sensors with limited memory capacity.

2 METHODS

Participants were from the San Francisco Bay Area in the US, and Singapore. Participants during the whole duration of the study were not taking any medication, were non-smokers and were not heavy alcohol drinkers. They were asked to wear the sensors both while indoors and outdoors. T_{sk} of the US participants was measured on the dorsal part of the forearm at 60 s intervals for approximately 1 month (Liu et al., 2019). T_{sk} of the Singaporean participants was measured on the anterior part of the forearm at 20 s intervals for a week. A 3D printed iButton® holder was designed and used to non-intrusively keep the iButton® in contact with the skin in anterior part of the forearm all times. The holder can be installed on any type of watch or wristband. T_{sk} of all participants was measured approximately 2 cm far from the wrist. The top-side of the iButton®, which has a faster response to temperature changes (van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006), was put in contact with the skin. We removed the data collected when

the sensor was not worn by the participant. Time series data was then down-sampled at multiples of 60 s intervals between 60 and 600 s. Down sampled time series data were interpolated using both linear and quadratic functions to determine the impact that the selection of the interpolation function had on the results. Interpolated data were then compared with the original data set. The following three metrics were used to report the results: i) the median absolute error which is a robust index insensitive to outliers; ii) the maximum error to capture the worst case error between the original dataset and the resampled one; and, iii) the 99 % quantile error. We believe that while it is important to know the worst case error, this metric alone would not be meaningful. In longitudinal thermal comfort studies participants would only be asked to complete thermal comfort surveys maximum 24 times per days. Hence, the authors believed that the 99 % quantile error is a more useful metrics since does not include errors caused by the 1 % of the fastest temperature transients. It should also be noted that iButtons® in water, which has higher heat capacity and conductivity than skin, have a time constant of 19 s (van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006). Arguably then iButtons® should not be used in thermal comfort studies interested in determine subjects' thermal perceptions during transient conditions (e.g. when human move between two spaces at different temperatures) or when T_{sk} rate of change is higher than 1 °C per minute (van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006). Participants should also be informed to wait at least 10 minutes before completing the survey after changing location, activity or clothing if iButtons® are used. Decision was taken not to use any filter to remove outliers nor to remove noise from the measurements. Since that could smooth out some rapid temperature fluctuations.

3 RESULTS

Among the 19 participants who took part in this study. A total of 14 (6 females and 8 males) were living in California, while 5 participants were living in Singapore. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the T_{sk} measured for each participants.

Figure 1 Skin temperature of the study participants.

For the Singaporean participants, 95 % of the T_{sk} data ranged between 31.4 °C and 35.8 °C. Data from these subjects was collected in October 2019 (outdoor temperature between 25 °C and 32 °C) which is characterized by a hot and humid climate. While for the US participants 95 % of the T_{sk} data varied between 27.3 °C and 35.7 °C. Some of the US subjects may have been exposed to outdoor temperatures lower than 10 °C since data was collected across different seasons between October 2016 and June 2017. Figure 2 shows side by side the errors distribution at different sampling periods using the linear and quadratic interpolation functions. The errors proportionally increased with the sampling interval. While the errors were lower with the quadratic interpolation, no relevant difference was found between the two methods.

Figure 2 a) Maximum error; b) median absolute error; and, c) 99% quantile error for different sampling periods. The width of the violins is scaled by the number of observations for each period bin. Each violin shows side by side the errors generated by the linear and quadratic interpolation.

4 DISCUSSION

The selection of the sampling period should depend on study objectives and requirements. Sampling periods lower than 60 s should be used in field thermal comfort studies which aim to determine how people's perceptions and physiological parameters vary during transient situations. For example, during step down transients (from 32 °C to 24 °C) T_{sk} has been observed to rapidly change within the first minute while reaching a new steady state in approximately 10 minutes (Chen et al., 2011). iButtons® have a time constant higher than 19 s hence they should be used with caution to measure T_{sk} during transients conditions (van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006). Conversely, sampling periods higher than 60 s can be used if participants are asked to complete right-here-right-now surveys after being in steady state conditions (i.e. constant clothing, metabolic rate and indoor air temperature) for a given time (e.g. 10 minutes) which increases proportionally to the magnitude of the change they were exposed to. We found that with sampling periods as high as 480 s the maximum median absolute error was lower than 0.1 °C with both interpolation methods, where 0.1 °C is the temperature sensor accuracy (range between 25 °C and 40 °C) needed to measure skin temperature

according to the ISO Standard 9886 (ISO, 2004). This can be explained by the fact that skin temperature in the extremities has low fluctuations when environmental (i.e. air temperature and velocity) and personal parameters are kept constant (Chen et al., 2011; Xiong et al., 2016). These conditions most likely occurred when participants were indoors and did not modify their clothing or activity levels. However, it should be noted that the 99th percentile of the errors for some of the participants was higher than 1 °C at 420 s sampling period. This should then be added to the error caused by the thermal inertia of the sensor which can reach up to 1°C (van Marken Lichtenbelt et al., 2006). We believe that with the current existing technological limitations, in longitudinal thermal comfort studies which are limited to steady-state conditions and use iButtons®, the optimal sampling period is 300 s. This sampling period would provide accurate results while limiting the burden on the occupants since it is the shortest sampling period of the DS1925 iButtons®. DS1925 can store up to 61K readings and log data continuously for a period of approximately 211 days. Based on our results we expect that if participants are asked to complete right-here-right-now surveys after being in almost a steady state condition the error in T_{sk} measurements will be lower than the maximum median absolute error (0.05 °C). This would have negligible effect on the results, while making it possible to continuously log T_{sk} in longitudinal field studies where wired instruments are impractical. where wired instruments are impractical.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we determined how the selection of the sampling period affects the measurement errors in longitudinal thermal comfort field studies that utilize wireless sensors with limited memory capacity to measure skin temperature. We believe that these results will help researchers to better select the optimal sampling period at which T_{sk} needs be measured based on their specific experimental constraints and requirements. Results showed that the selection of a 300 s would provide accurate results if participants are asked to complete right-here-right now surveys in steady-state conditions while allowing researchers to continuously log data for 211 days. With sampling period of 300 s the median absolute error was 0.05 °C which is lower than the sensor accuracy to comply with ISO 9886 and 99th maximum percentile error was 0.79 °C.

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